

Analysis Plan

Quality assessment of a newly established laboratory for Optically Pumped Magnetometry (OPM)

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1 Introduction

This document details the analysis plan of the project “Quality assessment of a newly established laboratory for Optically Pumped Magnetometry (OPM)”. This analysis plan was completed and pre-registered on Zenodo prior to the begin of data analysis. It specifies both the preprocessing and the statistical analyses of our acquired data ex ante, i.e. prior to data analysis.

The objective of this quality control project is to assess the quality and stability of measurements obtained with a newly established laboratory setup using optically pumped magnetometers (OPM) for magnetoencephalography (MEG). In addition to measurements of background noise using a phantom (not part of this analysis plan), this quality assessment study investigates a well-established neurophysiological signal in human EEG and MEG, the auditory mismatch response, also known as mismatch negativity (MMN), and assesses its test-retest reliability when measured with the new OPM setup.

Importantly, the goal of this quality control project is not to gain any novel insights into brain function, but focuses entirely on the quality and reliability of our new OPM-MEG setup.

2 Main hypothesis and goals

The goal of this quality assurance project is twofold. First, we examine whether we obtain MMN responses (in terms of event-related fields) with our OPM-MEG setup that are qualitatively comparable to previous MMN findings in the MEG and EEG literature. Second, we will assess the stability of the measurements using a test-retest analysis. The two main hypotheses to be tested are therefore:

- H1 OPM-MEG recordings with our setup show auditory mismatch negativity responses which are qualitatively comparable to MMN responses as previously demonstrated with conventional (SQUID-based) MEG and EEG, respectively.
- H2 Significant MMN responses recorded by our OPM-MEG setup show high test-retest reliability with regard to amplitude and latency.

Since the exact timing and location of MMN responses depend on numerous factors – in particular the measurement technique, experimental paradigm, and type of mismatch – H1 can only be tested in a qualitative fashion. In particular, we will focus on the following qualitative comparisons:

- Same mismatch type, same paradigm, different measurement technique:
Do significant MMN responses measured by OPM-MEG occur in a comparable time window as MMN responses measured by EEG under the same paradigm (Weber et al., 2022)?
- Same mismatch type, different paradigm, different measurement technique:
Do MMN responses measured by OPM-MEG occur in a comparable time window as MMN responses measured by SQUID-based MEG in previous studies that used different auditory MMN paradigms but also focused on frequency deviants? This question will be addressed focusing both on single sensors in comparable locations (e.g. Figure 2 of (Maess et al., 2007)) and hemisphere-specific grand averages (e.g. Figure 3 of (Maess et al., 2007)).

3 Experimental design and data

For this study, complete datasets were collected from 30 participants. OPM-MEG data were acquired while participants performed the same auditory mismatch negativity task as in (Weber et al., 2022). During the task, participants were engaged in a visual distractor task. Please see Weber et al. (2022) for details of the experimental paradigm.

3.1 OPM-MEG data acquisition

Continuous OPM-MEG data were recorded inside a magnetically shielded room, which is optimized for OPM operation using demagnetization coils and a matrix coil system for dynamic field nulling (Cerca Magnetics Limited, Nottingham, UK). The OPM data of a 64-sensor array of triaxial zero-field OPM sensors (QuSpin Inc., Louisville, CO, USA) were sampled at 1200 Hz using a series of National Instruments (NI, Austin, TX, USA) NI-9205 16-bit analogue to digital converters interfaced with LabVIEW (NI, Austin, TX, USA). The sensors were mounted inside 3D-printed rigid helmets (Cerca Magnetics Limited, Nottingham, UK) according to head sizes. Each participant was invited to two separate sessions recorded at the same time of the day (+/-2h). The second session was recorded between 1-3 days after the first session. For each individual, we assured that the OPM helmet was placed in similar positions between the two sessions by adjusting the distance between the rim of the helmet and the tip of the participant's nose in the second session to match the one measured in the first.

3.2 Auditory MMN paradigm

During the experiment, participants listened to a tone sequence consisting of low (440 Hz) and high tones (528 Hz). The stimulus onset asynchrony (SOA) of tones was 570ms with a stimulus duration (SOT) of 70ms. Stimuli were presented in a roving order. The probability of hearing either the low or the high tone at any point during the sequence varied according to a pre-defined schedule (see Figure 1 in Weber et al. 2022). During the entire experiment, participants performed a distractor task, which required them to focus their attention on a square presented centrally on a screen in front of them and to indicate via a button press whenever the square opened either on the left or the right side. For a detailed description, please see (Weber et al., 2022).

4 Preprocessing of OPM MEG data

4.1 OPM MEG data

The raw OPM MEG data will be preprocessed using MATLAB and SPM12. For preprocessing, the following steps will be performed sequentially on the continuous raw MEG recordings:

The raw MEG data will be notch-filtered to remove 50Hz power line noise, high-pass filtered using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with cutoff frequency 0.1 Hz, low-pass filtered using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with cutoff frequency 30 Hz.

We will then use adaptive multipole models (Tierney et al., 2024) to remove global signals not originating from the brain. Finally, we will downsample the data to 240 Hz.

The data will then be epoched into 500 ms segments around tone onsets, using a pre-stimulus time window of 100 ms. We will apply baseline correction by subtracting the average of a 100 ms pre-stimulus time-window for each sensor direction to account for slow drifts in the data.

Control analysis: The settings of the high-pass filter (0.1 Hz) follow (Weber et al., 2022), but often a higher cutoff is chosen. As a control, we will, therefore, re-run the analysis pipeline using a high-pass filter of 1 Hz, instead of 0.1 Hz.

4.2 Artefact removal

Trials in which the amplitude of the measured data of any channel exceeds 3 times the standard deviation of that channel will be removed from subsequent analysis. In addition, we will remove all trials whose tone was presented within 1000 ms after the opening of the fixation stimulus of the distractor task.

4.3 Reason for exclusion of data sets

In order to assure quality of data that enters the statistical analysis, a set of criteria for exclusion of datasets are defined a priori. We aim for the thresholds stated below. However, these thresholds will be reconsidered if they lead to exclusion of more than 10% of participants. Any potential decision to adjust the exclusion criteria will be taken and documented before any statistical analyses of the data are conducted. Reasons for excluding data sets from the analysis will be:

- Technical issues of data acquisition that were not visible during the measurements but only become apparent during quality control and preprocessing of the data.
- Excessive number of trials contaminated by artefacts (more than 20%) or more than 10% of bad channels.

4.4 Computation of magnetic field magnitude

Finally, we will compute the magnitude of the magnetic field at each sensor location, by computing the length of the magnetic field vector using the L2-norm. This magnitude will be used for all further analysis.

This approach exploits the fact that our new setup contains the most recent generation of OPM sensors, i.e. tri-axial sensors. Since we are lacking experience with these sensors, we specify an alternative approach in case of unexpected difficulties. This alternative approach is comparable to the previous test-retest analysis of auditory MMN using SQUID-based MEG (Recasens & Uhlhaas 2017) and rests on using only the radial fields in order to compute planar gradiometers, i.e. the magnitude of the 2D gradient of the z field.

5 Classical event related field analysis

5.1 Purpose

The conventional event related field (ERF) MMN analysis serves to test hypothesis H1.

5.2 Trial definition

For the analysis related to hypothesis H1, we will define deviants and standards within the stimulus sequence in the same way as in a previous study that used the same oddball MMN design we use here (Weber et al., 2022). A deviant trial is defined as the first auditory stimulus of a different frequency after at least 5 repetitions of the same tone. A standard trial is defined as the sixth repetition of the same stimulus type. This procedure yields 106 standard and 119 deviant trials from a total of 1800 trials. Note that our analysis will not consider the factor 'volatility', i.e. the change between stable and instable phases.

5.3 Realignment of helmet orientation

While all analysis will be conducted in sensor space, we will use the measured helmet rim to tip of the nose distances to rotate the acquired sensor data in the sagittal plane in a way such that the helmet to head alignment becomes - within one sensor position – identical across subjects.

5.4 Conversion to images and smoothing

For the following ERF analysis, the preprocessed MEG files containing all trials of the two conditions per participant are converted into 4D (scalp \times within trial time points \times trials) images. This results in two 4D images (one per condition) per participant. Subsequently, spatial smoothing will be performed with a Gaussian kernel of 16 mm FWHM in both spatial dimensions. It is important to note that smoothing will support the group level analysis by making it less sensitive to potential variations of re-alignment accuracy across subjects. Crucially, the realignment of the two sessions within each subject was carefully controlled by adjusting the distance between the nose and the rim of the helmet to exactly match the first session.

5.5 First level analysis

Per participant, we will enter the 4D ERF images into a general linear model (GLM) implementing a within-sample (paired) t-test comparing standard and deviant tones. Hence, we will assume that the two conditions have the same variance (i.e., identity) but are correlated (non-independence). We will compute the following contrast on the first level GLM:

- standards > deviants (main effect of mismatch)

The first level GLM serves to provide the contrast images used for the group-level analysis. On the group level, we will examine this contrast in both directions to investigate Hypothesis H1.

5.6 Group level analysis

Using the contrast images provided by the first level analyses above, we will examine the following group-level effects:

- average positive MMN across group
- average negative MMN across groups

These contrasts will be tested using one-tailed one-sample t-tests. We will apply a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$, family-wise error (FWE) corrected for multiple comparison at the peak level using Gaussian random field theory. Given the lack of experience we (and the field in general) currently have with respect to group-level effects measured by OPM-MEG, it is possible that group effects are not necessarily observed as focal effects (that would be commensurate with peak-level FWE correction) but might instead materialise as more spatially distributed effects (that would require cluster-level FWE correction). Therefore, as an alternative, we will use cluster-level FWE correction at $p < 0.05$, using Gaussian random field theory, with a cluster-defining threshold of $p < 0.001$.

This group analysis will be conducted for both sessions separately and the results will be compared qualitatively by displaying the resulting clusters and t-maps. Timeseries (at the sensor level) from significant peaks (or clusters, respectively) will be used for the test-retest analysis across the two sessions, as described in the next section.

6 Test-retest analysis

In order to assess the test-retest reliability of the MMN measured with the new OPM setup, we will conduct the following analysis using a similar strategy to (Recasens and Uhlhaas, 2017).

6.1 Selection of sensors for test retest analysis

We will use the group results of the first session to select the sensors associated with the significant peaks or clusters, respectively, of the group analysis. For each of these sensors, we will determine the timing and amplitude of maximum deviation between -50 ms and 50 ms around the maximum deviation of the group average within that electrode.

6.2 MEG features for test-retest analysis

For the test-retest analysis we plan to use similar metrics as (Recasens and Uhlhaas, 2017). Specifically, we will extract the following two features for each subject, each of the selected sensors and each session:

1. Average amplitude between -10ms to +10ms around the sensor-specific maximum (minimum) which, as described above, is determined within a time window of ± 50 ms around the group maximum (minimum).
2. Response latency (in ms after stimulus onset) of the maximum (minimum) which is determined within a time window of ± 50 ms around the latency of the group effect.

(Maximum or minimum will be chosen depending on whether the group analysis revealed a maximum or minimum.)

Using these measures, we will compute the intra-class correlation coefficient ICC(3,1) according to the definition by Shrout & Fleiss (1979) and as reviewed in (Liljequist et al., 2019) as ICC(C,1):

$$ICC(C, 1) = \frac{MSBS - MSE}{MSBS + (k-1) \cdot MSE}$$

where $k=2$ is the number of measurements, and the mean square between subjects (MSBS) and mean squared error (MSE) are computed according to (Liljequist et al., 2019).

Bibliography

- Liljequist, D., Elfving, B., Skavberg Roaldsen, K., 2019. Intraclass correlation – A discussion and demonstration of basic features. PLoS ONE 14, e0219854. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0219854>
- Maess, B., Jacobsen, T., Schröger, E., Friederici, A.D., 2007. Localizing pre-attentive auditory memory-based comparison: Magnetic mismatch negativity to pitch change. NeuroImage 37, 561–571. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2007.05.040>
- Recasens, M., Uhlhaas, P.J., 2017. Test–retest reliability of the magnetic mismatch negativity response to sound duration and omission deviants. NeuroImage 157, 184–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.05.064>
- Shrout, P.E., Fleiss, J.L., 1979. Intraclass correlations: Uses in assessing rater reliability. Psychological Bulletin 86, 420–428. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.86.2.420>
- Tierney, T.M., Seedat, Z., St Pier, K., Mellor, S., Barnes, G.R., 2024. Adaptive multipole models of OPTICALLY PUMPED MAGNETOMETER data. Human Brain Mapping 45, e26596. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.26596>
- Weber, L.A., Tomiello, S., Schöbi, D., Wellstein, K.V., Mueller, D., Iglesias, S., Stephan, K.E., 2022. Auditory mismatch responses are differentially sensitive to changes in muscarinic acetylcholine versus dopamine receptor function. eLife 11, e74835. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.74835>